

ratoon rice - submerged fallow. The remaining farmers grow rice - ratoon rice - wheat.

In 1989, ratoon rice was on 0.45 million ha. Average yield of the main crop was about 7 t/ha, average yield of the ratoon crop was 1.6 t/ha (Table 1). Maximum ratoon yield was 4 t/ha. The ratoon crop has a short growth duration (about 60 d) and costs less than a second transplanted crop because it eliminates three major crop establishment operations: raising seedlings in the seedbed, field plowing, and transplanting.

Hybrid rices are planted in 85% of the total rice area in Sichuan. Some hybrids not only are high grain yielding but also have high ratooning ability. Hybrid rice ratoon crops yield 17% higher than conventional rice ratoon crops (Table 2). At present, the leading hybrid rice combinations Shanyou 63 and D-you 63 are most suitable for ratooning.

To make rice ratooning productive and economical, a package of main and ratoon crop management practices is rec-

Table 1. Area and yield of ratoon rice in Sichuan Province, China, 1986-90.

Year	Area (10 ⁴ ha)	Yield (t/ha)
1986	4.6	1.1
1987	19.3	1.5
1988	28.3	1.3
1989	45.0	1.6
1990	34.5	1.3

ommended. The main crop nursery is sown in early Mar. Seedlings are raised under a plastic film or in a greenhouse, then transplanted at 33- × 13.3-cm spacing to reduce sheath blight. Rice is grown on ridges and fish in the ditches. Applying urea at 45-68 kg N/ha 2 wk before harvesting the main crop delays main crop senescence to produce more ratoon tillers and panicles. In fields with P deficiency, applying P fertilizer to the main crop significantly increases ratoon yield.

The main crop is harvested when nearly mature and when ratoon shoots have just begun to grow (3-5 cm).

Table 2. Grain yield of main and ratoon crops of some rice varieties in Jiangjin, Sichuan, China, 1986.^a

Type	Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)		
		Main crop	Ratoon crop	Total
Hybrid	Shanyou 63	8.6 a	2.0 a	10.6 a
Hybrid	D-you 63	8.5 a	2.0 a	10.5 a
Hybrid	V-you 63	8.5 a	1.7 a	10.2 ab
Hybrid	Gangai 63	7.6 b	2.1 a	9.7 bc
Hybrid	Zaishengyou	7.8 b	1.6 a	9.4 c
Conventional	40-1	6.9 c	2.1 a	9.0 d
Conventional	Daonan 18	6.6 c	1.7 a	8.3 e

^a Av of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Optimum cutting height is 30-40 cm aboveground.

Inadequate fertilizer and low temperature injury at ratoon rice heading are the major factors associated with low ratoon crop yields. Breeders are selecting hybrid rices for intermediate to early maturity, high yield in the main crop, and strong ratooning ability. □

Farm machinery

Ideal seed drill for direct sowing rice in semidry fields

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Rice crops that are broadcast seeded by hand in semidry fields have poor stands and low productivity. We compared two seeding techniques during 1990 wet season (WS). The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with 14 replications.

Soil was clay loam (fine Udic Chromusterts) with pH 6.8, 0.78% organic C; 300, 35, and 127 kg available NPK/ha. Rice cultivar CR1009 was seeded in dry soil in Aug, at 80 kg/ha. Fertilizer (150-60-60 kg NPK/ha) was applied at different stages of crop growth. The crop was flooded 30 d after seed germination.

The crop sown in lines with a three-tined, cupfeed type, bullock-drawn seed

Effect of rice seeding technique on yield and net income at Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India, 1990 WS.

Seeding method	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Panicles/hill	Grain yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit:cost ratio
Line drill-sown	95.7	9.9	8.3	5.8	425	1.27
Broadcast	94.2	8.6	6.1	5.2	333	1.10
LSD (0.05)	ns	1.1	0.7	0.2		

drill had the best yield attributes, resulting in a significantly higher yield (12.4% more than with conventional broadcast-

ing) (see table). Gross income, net return, and benefit:cost ratio were also higher. □

Efficiency of a compartment-type rice separator

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Separating rough rice from brown rice is an important operation of modern rice mills: it avoids damage to polisher parts

from the abrasive action of rice husks. Unhusked rice that goes through a polisher may also affect overall mill capacity.

A compartment separator (Schule-type) is more commonly used in modern rice mills than tray and screen type separators. We evaluated the effect of stroke length and slope of deck on separation, capacity, and energy consumption of a compartment-type paddy separator manufactured in India.

The separator has two outlets; three compartments with a single deck; and adjustments for feed control, slope, and

stroke length. Variables considered were 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 degree table slopes and 140, 150, 160, and 170 mm stroke lengths. A mixture of brown rice to rough rice of 9:1 was taken at a feed rate of 220 kg/h. The separator was run with a particular set of adjustments.

Samples (100 g) were collected from both outlets at three different times.

Effectiveness of separation was highest at a 1-2 degree slope, with stroke length 150-165 mm. In general, processing capacity increased with table slope and stroke length. Energy consumption

decreased with an increase in table slope and increased with an increase in stroke length.

When the separator is set up with a 1-2 degree table slope and 150-165 mm stroke length, a feed rate of 220 kg/h gave the best performance. □

SOCIOECONOMIC IMPACT

Environmental impacts

Impact of agrochemicals on mosquito larvae populations in ricefields

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As part of an experiment to study the impacts of agrochemical use on floodwater and soil ecology in wetland ricefields, we investigated the combined effects of N fertilizer and two widely used pesticides—carbofuran and butachlor—on mosquito larvae in irrigated fields at the IRRI farm during 1990 dry season. The experiment involved 65 16-m²-plots, with five replications. Treatments were

- one unplanted unfertilized control.
- ten combinations of five N treatments (no N, 55 and 110 kg N/ha broadcast split, 55 kg N/ha-deep placed, and azolla incorporated before transplanting) and two levels of carbofuran (one at 0.1 kg active ingredient [ai]/ha and two at 0.3 kg/ha each).
- two additional treatments with 110 kg N/ha broadcast split combined with two applications of 0.5 kg carbofuran/ha each and five applications of 0.5 kg/ha each. Treatments with two and five applications of carbofuran also received one application of 0.375 kg ai butachlor/ha 3 d after transplanting (DT).

Pesticide rates represent low, medium, and high levels as commonly used by farmers in the Philippines.

Population density of mosquito larvae was determined by counting individuals in five samples collected by inserting 7-cm-diameter clear perspex cylinders into the soil and removing the enclosed floodwater and surface soil with a vacuum pump.

Mosquito larvae, tentatively identified as *Aedes davidi*, developed populations larger than 100/m² only during the first third of the crop cycle, peaking at about 16 DT. Largest populations—2000-3500 larvae/m²—were in plots where inorganic N fertilizer was broadcast (Fig. 1). Population density remained lower than 300/m² in plots where N fertilizer was deep-placed, azolla was incorporated, and

1. Dynamics of mosquito larvae populations during a crop cycle under different N fertilizer inputs. Variance analysis at 12 and 16 DT shows no significant differences between no N and 55 kg N deep-placed. N broadcast at 55 kg showed significantly higher numbers than no N and 55 kg N deep-placed. N broadcast at 110 kg gave significantly higher numbers than 55 kg N broadcast. Each value is the average of 8 (N0, 55 kg N broadcast, 55 kg N deep-placed) or 16 (1 10 kg N broadcast) plots.